

International Journal of Advances in Engineering & Scientific Research (IJAESR)

ISSN: 2349 -3607 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 -4824 (Print)

Available online at:

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-1-issue-2-june-2014-0>

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DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF FULLY REVERSED AXIAL LOADING FATIGUE TESTING MACHINE

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Abstract

From the decades of moving machine elements become more important and lifetime approach in fatigue design based on S-N curves establishes for an infinity life where the applied stress cycle is below than endurance limit. After fatigue test in results we got the fatigue failure beyond 10^6 cycles even this test indicates there is no endurance fatigue limit, from the various servo-hydraulic testing machine we got the late results and its very time consuming as well as expensive tests. Reciprocating fatigue testing equipment for laboratory use is a new generation of devices designed to perform tests in a very short time. This thesis describes the design and assembly of reciprocating fatigue testing equipment working at 50 kHz. From this research paper, the obtained designed is a complete balanced system of a forced control unit and implemented on purely mechanical fatigue test equipment is design and developed. This testing machine consist a revolution counter, electric motor, pulley system and an external mechanical structure to hold the specimen which is the main reason for the overall cheap price. The result of this study will contribute to prolonged use of fatigue testing equipment.

Keywords: fatigue test, reverse axial loading machine, s-n curve, reciprocating fatigue testing

1.1 Introduction

It is very complex for predicting the fatigue failure for structural elements to variable loading condition. The first, simplest, and most widely used damage model is the linear damage. This rule is often referred to as Miner's rule (1945). However, in many cases the linear rule often leads to non-conservative life predictions. The results from this approach do not take into account the effect of load sequence on the accumulation of damage fatigue due to cyclic loading.[1]

1.2 Fatigue of Structures and Materials

Fatigue failures in metallic structures are a well-known phenomenon. The failures were already observed in the 19th century, and the first investigations on fatigue were carried out in that time. Noteworthy engineering research on fatigue was done by August Wöhler. He recognized that a single load application, far below the static strength of a structure, did not do any damage to the structure. However, if the same load was repeated many times it could induce a complete failure.[2]

The material fails by fatigue which is not be seen in the 19th century fatigue was thought to be a shadowy phenomenon. Since 20th century the study started for the repeated load application as a fatigue mechanism in the materials for a microcracks, crack growth, and ultimately to complete fatigue failure of a structure. The history of engineering structures until now has been marked by numerous fatigue failures of machinery, moving vehicles, welded structures, aircraft, etc. From time to time such failures have caused a catastrophic accident [2], such as an explosion or complete failure of a bridge or other large structures. However, numerous fatigue problems do not reach the headlines of the newspapers although the economic impact of non-catastrophic fatigue failures can be tremendous.

1.3 Fatigue Damage Mechanism

When the material is subject to repeated loading and material meets micro-cracks or cracks nucleus can be initiated, further meets macro-cracks and finally specimen failure in the last cycle of the fatigue life.

Understanding of the fatigue mechanism is essential for considering various technical conditions which affect fatigue life and fatigue crack growth, such as the material surface quality, residual stress, and environmental influence.[3]

This knowledge is essential for the analysis of fatigue properties of an engineering structure. Fatigue prediction methods can only be evaluated if fatigue is understood as a crack initiation process followed by a crack growth period. Fatigue is a localized damage process of a component produced by cyclic loading. It is the result of the cumulative process consisting of crack initiation, propagation, and final fracture of a component.[4, 5] . During cyclic loading, localized plastic deformation may occur at the highest stress site. This plastic deformation induces permanent damage to the component and a crack develops. As the component experiences an increasing number of loading cycles, the length of the crack (damage) increases. After a certain number of cycles, the crack will cause the component to fail (separate).[6,7,8]

1.4 Purposes of Fatigue Test

The literature on fatigue problems illustrates the large variety of purposes of fatigue investigations. Some categories are:

1. Collecting data on material fatigue properties for material selection by the designer.
2. Investigations on effects of different surface finishes and production techniques.
4. Investigations on environmental effects.
5. Investigations on crack nucleation and crack propagation.
6. Verification of fatigue prediction models.

Although other lists can be compiled, it is obvious that the choice of experimental variables will depend on the type of investigation to be carried out. Major variables to be selected are: (i) type of specimen, (ii) fatigue loads, (iii) testing procedures.

The main purpose of an investigation may be a comparison of fatigue properties for different conditions, e.g. different surface conditions. It implies comparative fatigue tests. In other test series, the objective can be a determination of specific fatigue properties for a single condition, e.g. the determination of crack growth properties of a material.

1.5 Design Consideration for Fatigue Testing Machine

The machine members are found to have failed under the action of repeated or fluctuating stresses; yet the most careful analysis reveals that the actual maximum stresses were well below the ultimate strength of the material, and quite frequently even below the yield strength. The most distinguishing characteristic of these failures is that the stresses have been repeated a very large number of times. Hence the failure is called fatigue failure.

When machine parts fail statically, they usually develop a very large deflection, because the stress has exceeded the yield strength, and the part is replaced before fracture actually occurs. Thus many static failures give visible warning in advance. But a fatigue failure gives no warning! It is sudden and total, and hence dangerous. It is relatively simple to design against a static failure, because our knowledge is comprehensive. Fatigue is much more complicated phenomenon, only partially understood, and the engineer seeking competence must acquire as much knowledge of the subject as possible.

A fatigue failure has an appearance similar to a brittle fracture, as the fracture surfaces are flat and perpendicular to the stress axis with the absence of necking. The fracture features of a fatigue failure, however, are quite different from a static brittle fracture arising from three stages of development.

Stage 1: The initiation of one or more micro cracks due to cyclic plastic deformation followed by crystallographic propagation extending from two to five grains about the origin. Stage 1 cracks are not normally discernible to the naked eye.

Stage 2: Progresses from microcracks to macrocracks forming parallel plateau-like fracture surfaces separated by longitudinal ridges. The plateaus are generally smooth and normal to the direction of maximum tensile stress. During cyclic loading, these cracked surfaces open and close, rubbing together, and the beach mark appearance depends on the changes in the level or frequency of loading and the corrosive nature of the environment.

Stage 3 : Occurs during the final stress cycle when the remaining material cannot support the loads, resulting in a sudden, fast fracture. A stage 3 fracture can be brittle, ductile, or a combination of both. Quite often the beach marks, if they exist, and possible patterns in the stage 3 fracture called chevron lines, point toward the origins of the initial cracks.[9,10]

2. Design Objective and Design of Machine Parts

This aims at designing and constructing a fatigue testing machine that is capable of testing the fatigue life of various samples of specimen from metals, such as mild steel, aluminium, brass, etc.

Also with the result of each test carried out with this machine, the fatigue life of various materials can be obtained and fatigue failure be guarded against in an optimum manner. [9]

2.1 Design of Belt Drive

Length of an open belt drive:

where,

$$\sin \alpha = \frac{R_E - R_A}{l} = \frac{101.6 - 25.4}{250} = \frac{76.2}{250}$$

$$\alpha = \sin^{-1}(0.3048) = 17.75^\circ$$

$$\text{Length of belt, } L = \pi (R_A + R_B) + 2l + \frac{(R_E - R_A)^2}{l}$$

$$L = \pi (25.4 + 101.6) + 2 \times 250 + \frac{(76.2)^2}{250}$$

$$L = 922.2 \text{ mm}$$

$$L = 0.9222 \text{ m}$$

Figure 1: Open Belt Drive (Belt Length)

2.2 Ratio of Tensions:

$$2.3 \log (T_1/T_2) = \mu\theta$$

$$2.3 \log (T_1/T_2) = 0.25 \times 2.522$$

$$(T_1/T_2) = e^{0.6305}$$

$$(T_1/T_2) = 1.88 \quad \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

2.3 Power Transmission by Belt:

Power of motor used in machine = 0.5 H.P.

$$P = 373 \text{ watt.}$$

Let, T_1 = the tension in the tight side

T_2 = the tension in the slack side

v = the velocity of belt.

$$\text{Power} = (T_1 - T_2) \times v$$

Speed of driver pulley A (N_A) = 1440 rpm

$$\text{Angular velocity } \omega = \omega_A = \frac{2\pi N_A}{60} \text{ Rad/sec}$$

$$= \omega_A = \frac{2\pi(1440)}{60} \text{ Rad/sec}$$

$$= \omega_A = 48\pi \text{ Rad/sec}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Tangential velocity } V_A &= \omega_A r_A \\
 \text{Tangential velocity } V_A &= 48 \times \pi \times 25.4 \\
 &= 3830 \text{ mm/s} \\
 &= 3.83 \text{ m/s} \\
 (T_1 - T_2) &= 373 / 3.83 \\
 &= 97.39 \text{ N} \qquad \dots\dots\dots (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

From equation (1)

$$T_1 = 1.88 T_2$$

Put in equation (2), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 1.88 T_2 - T_2 &= 97.39 \\
 0.88 T_2 &= 97.39 \\
 T_2 &= 97.39 / 0.88 \\
 T_2 &= 110.67 \text{ N} \\
 T_1 &= 208.06 \text{ N}
 \end{aligned}$$

2.4 Design of Shaft:

Load on shaft:

Total load on shaft due to tensions & weight of pulley

Figure: Free Body Diagram of Pulley

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= T_1 \cos \alpha + T_2 \cos \alpha - W \\
 &= (T_1 + T_2) \cos \alpha - W \\
 &= (110.67 + 208.06) \cos 17.75 - 9.24
 \end{aligned}$$

Total load = 294.32 N (upward direction)

Total load \approx 300 N approx.

SHEAR FORCE & BENDING MOMENT:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Shear force at A} &= 150 \text{ N} \\
 \text{Shear force at C} &= 150 - 300 \text{ N} \\
 &= -150 \text{ N} \\
 \text{Shear force at B} &= -150 \text{ N} \\
 \text{Bending Moment at A \& B} &= 0 \\
 \text{Bending Moment at C} &= 150 \times 40 \\
 &= 6,000 \text{ N-mm}
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 2: Free Body Diagram of Pulley

2.5 Torque Experience by Shaft:

Torque $T = (T_1 - T_2) \times \text{radius of pulley}$

$$= 97.39 \times 101.6$$

$$= 9894.824 \text{ N-mm} \quad \dots (3)$$

Alternate method:

$$\text{Power } P = \frac{2\pi N I}{60}$$

$$\text{Torque } T = \frac{P \times 60}{2\pi N}$$

$$= \frac{373 \times 60}{2\pi 360}$$

$$= 9,894.13 \text{ N-mm} \quad \dots (4)$$

from equation 3 & 4 we conclude that the approximate value of **Torque T = 9895 N**.

Figure 3: Torque Diagram

2.6 Shear Stress in Shaft:

$$\frac{T}{J} = \frac{\tau}{R}$$

$$\tau = \frac{T}{J} \times \frac{D}{2}$$

$$= \frac{16}{\pi} \times \frac{T}{D^3}$$

$$\tau = 6.3 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

Torque on Collar Shaft = 9895 Nmm

Force experienced by each bolt for fastening the shaft with adjusting block

$$4F = \frac{T}{R}$$

$$= \frac{9895}{22.5}$$

$$F = 110 \text{ N}$$

Force experienced by each bolt

Shear force on bolt = 110 N

Shear stress on bolt = $\frac{\text{Force}}{\text{Area}} = \frac{110}{28.27} = 3.89 \text{ N/mm}^2$

$\tau_{\text{bolt}} = 3.89 \text{ N/mm}^2$ on each bolt.

2.7 Shear Stress in the Collar of the Shaft:

Area of the collar = $\frac{\pi}{4} \cdot 60^2 = 2827.4 \text{ mm}^2$

Area of 4 (four) holes = $4 \cdot \frac{\pi}{4} \cdot 6.5^2 = 132.7 \text{ mm}^2$

Effective area of the collar = $2827.4 - 132.7$

$$A_{\text{Collar}} = 2,694.7 \text{ mm}^2$$

Effective diameter of collar = 58.6 mm

$$\frac{T}{J} = \frac{\tau}{R}$$

$$\tau = \frac{T}{J} \times \frac{D}{2}$$

$\tau = 0.032 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (Shear stress in collar shaft)

2.8 Strength of the Key:

A key connected to the shaft and hub is shown in the figure

Let, T = torque transmit by the shaft

F = tangential force acting at the circumference of the shaft.

D = diameter of the shaft

l = length of the key

w = width of the key

t = thickness of the key

τ = shear stress

σ_c = crushing stress

A little consideration will show that due to the power transmitted by the shaft, the key may fail due to shearing or crushing.

Figure 4: Key Diagram

A little consideration will show that due to the power transmitted by the shaft, the key may fail due to shearing or crushing.

Consider shearing of the key, the tangential shearing force

$$F = \text{Area resisting shearing} \times \text{Shear stress}$$

$$= l \times w \times \tau$$

2.9 Torque transmitted by shaft:

$$T = F \times d/2$$

$$= (l \times w \times \tau) \times d/2$$

Considering crushing of the key, The tangential crushing force acting at the circumference of the shaft

$$F = (\text{area resisting crushing}) \times (\text{crushing stress})$$

$$= l \times t/2 \times \sigma_c$$

Torque transmitted by the shaft

$$T = (l \times t/2 \times \sigma_c) \times d/2$$

The key is equally strong in shearing and crushing, if

$$l \times w \times \tau \times d/2 = (l \times t/2 \times \sigma_c) \times d/2$$

$$w/t = \sigma_c/2 \tau$$

The permissible crushing stress for the usual key material is at least twice the permissible shearing stress.

A square key is equally strong in shearing and crushing.

In order to find the length of the key to transmit full power of the shaft, the shearing strength of the key is equal to torsional shear strength of the shaft.

We know, $T = (l \times w \times \tau) \times d/2$

&

Torsional shear strength of the shaft,

$$T = \frac{\pi}{16} \cdot \tau_1 \cdot d^3$$

From eq. (4) & (5), we have

$$(l \times w \times \tau) \times d/2 = \frac{\pi}{16} \cdot \tau_1 \cdot d^3$$

$$l = 1.571 \times d \times \frac{\tau_1}{\tau} \text{ (taking } w = d/4 \text{)}$$

$$\frac{\tau_1}{\tau} = 1 \text{ (if material of the shaft and key is same)}$$

$$l = 1.571d$$

$$d = 20\text{mm of shaft}$$

Then the length of the key, $l = 31.42 \text{ (} l \approx 32 \text{)}$

3. Assembly and Development of Fatigue Testing Machine

Figure 5: Front View of Fatigue Testing Machine

Figure 6: Left View of Fatigue Testing Machine

4. Conclusions : Fatigue failure occurs when the fatigue stress is induced on a material due to the action of force reversing and fluctuating, a failure. This paper is basically on machine design where fatigue testing machines are developed. Fatigue failure cannot be predicted accurately meanwhile material failures under fatigue are affected by number of revolution (cycle per minute) and fluctuating stress and other factors such as temperature, atmospheric condition, both internal and external defects on material subjected under fatigue stress. Such defects include notch, inclusion, stress concentration and non-homogeneity.

References

- [1] L.N. Ojha H.B. Khurasia A.D. Telang, design and development of a reversed bending fatigue testing equipment for laboratory use, International Conference on Shot Peening and Blast Cleaning, Maulana Azad College of Technology, Bhopal, India.
- [2] M. Freitas, L. Reis, V. Anes, D. Montalvão, A. M. Ribeiro and M. Fonte, design and assembly of an ultrasonic fatigue testing machine, *Anales de Mecánica de la Fractura* 28, Vol. 1 (2011)
- [3] Ives De Baere, Design of a three- and four-point bending setup for fatigue testing of fibre-reinforced thermoplastics.
- [4] D. Brandolisio, G. Poelman, G. De Corte, J. Symynck, M. Juwet, F. De Bal, Rotating bending machine for high cycle fatigue testing.
- [5] Soon Bok Lee, Development of the deflection controlled multi-axial fatigue testing machine, *KSME Journal*, Vol 4, No.2, pp 103 -108, 1990.
- [6] G. Dahlberg, MTS Systems Corporation, Eden Prairie, USA, Dynamic Calibration of Axial Fatigue Testing Machines. Why is it important and how is it accomplished?, *EUROLAB International Workshop: Investigation and Verification of Materials Testing Machines*.
- [7] Hironori Nishihata, Shin-ichi Ohya and Yasuo Yoshioka, measurement of actual stresses during fatigue process, *Musashi Institute of Technology*, 1-28 Tamazutsumi, Setagaya, Tokyo 158, JAPAN.
- [8] V. Anes, D. Montalvão, A. Ribeiro, M. Freitas, M. Fonte, Design and instrumentation of an ultrasonic fatigue testing machine.
- [9] G. Junak*, M. Cieřla, Low-cycle fatigue of P91 and P92 steels used in the power engineering industry, *World Academy of Materials and Manufacturing Engineering*.
- [10] Gbasouzor Austine Ikechukwu, Design and characterization of a fatigue testing machine, proceedings of the world congress on engineering and computer science 2013 Vol I, *WCECS 2013*, 23-25 October, 2013